

Oxidation of 1,3-Dimethylthymine with Cumene Hydroperoxide catalysed by 5,10,15,20-Tetraarylporphyrinatomanganese(III) Chlorides

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We reported earlier¹ the oxidation of 1,3-dimethyluracil by cumene hydroperoxide (CumOOH) catalysed by 5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatomanganese(III) chlorides [TAPMn(III)Cl]. Thymine is more susceptible to oxidative modifications as compared to other bases of nucleic acids. Hence we report here the oxidation of 1,3-dimethylthymine (2) with cumene hydroperoxide catalysed by [TAPMn(III)Cl] (1). The condition of the experiments and results are presented in Chart 1.

Chart 1

Condition	Catalyst	Product yield (%)		
		HMDMU (3)	FDMU (4)	CDMU (5)
Dichloromethane/ room temp.	-	-	-	-
Dichloromethane/ NMeIm	TPPMnCl	3.0	30	-
Dichloromethane/ NMeIm/room temp.	Me ₁₂ TPPMnCl	4.0	79	-
Dichloromethane/ NMeIm/room temp.	Cl ₈ TPPMnCl	5.0	23	-
Dichloromethane/ NMeIm/room temp.	Cl ₈ TPPMnOAc	3.2	35	3

1,3-DMT (2): 1,3-dimethylthymine (Ref. 2); HMDMU (3): 5-hydroxy-methyl-1,3-dimethyluracil (Refs. 2, 3); FDMU; (4): 5-formyl-1,3-dimethyluracil (Ref. 4); CDMU (5): 5-carboxy-1,3-dimethyluracil (Ref. 5).

TPPMn(III)Cl (1): 5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrinatomanganese(III) chloride (R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H, X = Cl; Ref. 6)

Me₁₂TPPMn(III)Cl: 5,10,15,20-tetra(2',4',6'-trimethylphenyl)-porphyrinatomanganese(III) chloride (R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = CH₃, X = Cl; Refs. 7, 8)

Cl₈TPPMn(III)Cl: 5,10,15,20-tetra(2',6'-dichlorophenyl)porphyrinatomanganese(III) chloride (R₁ = H, R₂ = R₃ = Cl, X = Cl; Ref. 7)

Cl₈TPPMn(III)OAc: 5,10,15,20-tetra(2',6'-dichlorophenyl)porphyrinatomanganese(III) acetate (R₁ = H, R₂ = R₃ = Cl, X = OAc; Ref. 7)

The results indicate that sterically hindered and electron-withdrawing tetraarylporphyrins are the effective catalysts for the biomimetic oxidation of 1,3-dimethylthymine in organic solvents.

Experimental

Shimadzu IR-435, UV-260 and Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) nmr spectrometers were used. Thomas Hoover melting point apparatus and Waters HPLC with photodiode array detector were used.

Uracil and thymine (SRL, Bombay), cumene hydroperoxide and *N*-methylimidazole (Fluka) were used.

Procedure: Cumene hydroperoxide (70%; 0.03 g, 0.125 mmol) followed by *N*-methylimidazole (0.05 mmol) were slowly added to a stirred solution of 1,3-dimethylthymine (2; 77 mg, 0.5 mmol) and 5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatomanganese(III) halide (1; 0.05 mmol) in dichloromethane (10 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 2 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure, the residue dissolved in acetonitrile and subjected to hplc analysis for the identification of products. The formation of 5-formyl-1,3-dimethyluracil was also confirmed by spraying DNP reagent on tlc.

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